

HUMAN CONTROL, BIAS AND RISK

Mapping the discuss 2024 Group of Governmental Experts

The InterAgency Institute presents the preliminary results of a project seeking to map the Group of Governmental Experts on Lethal Autonomous Weapon Systems. After building a database with all the statements of the 2024 sessions, we identified how stakeholders make sense of three discursive categories: **human control, bias and risk**.*

HUMAN CONTROL

What are the **common grounds** in the operationalization of human control? The operationalization consists in specifying who should have control over what, when and how [1]. We have identified the following at the 2024 GGE sessions [2]:

BIAS

This section maps the way states addressed the issue of bias in their 2024 CCW statements [2]. It draws on an existing typology [3] that distinguishes three sources of bias. For analytical clarity, bias in society and in data processing were grouped as they both concern **bias within the system**, while bias in use refers to issues arising **during deployment**.

BIAS IN SOCIETY + DATA PROCESSING

Pre-existing skewing caused by historical inequalities, social institutions, practices or attitudes, as well as harmful properties introduced through choices and assumptions made during system design and development.

MENTIONS: 37 ■■■■■■■■■■■■

BIAS IN USE

Context of uses and interactions that were not anticipated at the design stage.

MENTIONS: 8 ■■■■■■■■■■

[1]. This taxonomy was proposed by Boulain, V., Davison, N., Goussac, N., & Peldán Carlsson, M. (2020). Limits on autonomy in weapon systems: Identifying practical elements of human control. Stockholm International Peace Research Institute & International Committee of the Red Cross.
[2]. You may find the database and an in-depth methodological explanation in the following links: Human Control: github.com/campaniluis/human_control_2024. Bias: github.com/manualefort/bias_2024.

R I S K

The 2024 discussions have introduced new **AWS-related risks** that were absent from the 2019 GGE Report [4]. Some states have proposed categorical frameworks to assess these risks, which we show in the graph below.

- **Dehumanization:** algorithmic bias; unintended bias; deadly racial discrimination; impact on the right to non-discrimination; indiscriminate effects;
- **Reliability:** unintended consequences; system failure; unpredictable behavior; erroneous decisions by the system or the operator; interactions/control over other systems;
- **Warfare:** unintentional conflicts; disproportionate use of force; asymmetric wars; fragmentation of existing international law;
- **Power gaps:** widening technological gap between the global North and South and other power gaps;
- **Human control:** lack of human control or human judgment; nominal participation of human beings (nominal human input);
- **Least mentioned:** health-related risks; impact on the environment;

State-suggested Risk categorizations

[3]. Blanchard, A., & Bruun, L. (2024). Bias in Military Artificial Intelligence: A Typology of Sources. Stockholm International Peace Research Institute.

[4]. United Nations, Report of the 2019 session of the Group of Governmental Experts on Emerging Technologies in the Area of Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems. CCW/GGE.1/2019/3, 25 September 2019, Annex IV

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